

OPTIMIZATION OF THE ROLE OF THE COOPERATIVE, SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (SMEs), AND TRADE OFFICE IN MONITORING THE DISTRIBUTION OF 3-KG LPG CYLINDERS IN BARRU REGENCY: A STUDY BASED ON LAW NO. 22 OF 2001 WITH ATLAS.ti ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the optimization of the role of the Cooperative, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), and Trade Office of Barru Regency in monitoring the distribution of 3-kg LPG cylinders, based on Law No. 22 of 2001 concerning Oil and Natural Gas. The 3-kg LPG cylinder is a subsidized commodity intended for low-income households and small businesses; therefore, its distribution monitoring is crucial to ensure accurate targeting and to prevent scarcity and misuse. This research employs a qualitative approach with data collected through in-depth interviews, observations, and documentation, and analyzed using Atlas.ti software to map the emerging key themes. The findings reveal that the role of the related office has been implemented through regulation, guidance, and field supervision. However, several challenges remain, including weak coordination with agents and distributors, limited supervisory resources, and lack of distribution transparency. The Atlas.ti analysis indicates that regulatory factors, distribution monitoring, agent involvement, and community participation are key to optimizing the management of 3-kg LPG distribution. Therefore, strengthening monitoring mechanisms, enhancing human resource capacity, and utilizing information technology for data transparency are required. This research contributes policy recommendations for local governments to ensure that the distribution of 3-kg LPG in Barru Regency becomes more effective, efficient, and well-targeted in accordance with the mandate of Law No. 22 of 2001.

Keywords: Optimization, Cooperative, SMEs, Trade, 3-kg LPG Distribution, Monitoring, Atlas.ti

INTRODUCTION

Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) in 3-kg cylinders is one of the most crucial subsidized energy commodities for low-income communities in Indonesia. The subsidy aims to protect poor households and microenterprises so that they can maintain access to affordable energy. However, the distribution of 3-kg LPG across various regions continues to face serious challenges, such as shortages, misuse of allocation, and price disparities at the consumer level (BPK RI, 2001). Barru Regency, as a region dominated by SMEs, requires optimal supervision to ensure that the distribution of subsidized LPG runs in accordance with its intended purpose.

The legal foundation for energy management in Indonesia is contained in Law No. 22 of 2001 on Oil and Gas, which emphasizes that oil and gas are vital resources controlled by the state for the prosperity of the people (BPK RI, 2001). The core principle of this law is the sovereignty of the state in regulating production, distribution, and pricing of oil and gas, including 3-kg

LPG. Therefore, the distribution of 3-kg LPG must be strictly monitored to ensure that the subsidy truly reaches the designated target groups. In this context, the role of the Cooperative, SMEs, and Trade Office (KUKMP) becomes essential for the implementation of policy at the regional level.

The government further strengthened the legal framework through Presidential Regulation No. 70 of 2021, which revised Presidential Regulation No. 104 of 2007 on the Provision, Distribution, and Pricing of Certain Types of LPG. This regulation serves as a reference for the distribution of 3-kg LPG, including restrictions on target recipients and price monitoring (BPK RI, 2021).

Consequently, local governments hold stronger legitimacy to regulate and supervise distribution. The KUKMP Office in Barru must be able to translate national regulations into concrete operational steps.

Since 2023, the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources (MEMR) has required the registration of 3-kg LPG consumers through a “by name by address” system to ensure targeted subsidy allocation (MEMR, 2023a). This registration relies not only on administrative data but also on field verification, which can be conducted by local governments. Such a system demands active involvement of the KUKMP Office in validating data and providing public education. Without local participation, the transformation of LPG distribution will face many obstacles.

In 2024, the Directorate General of Oil and Gas reaffirmed the importance of supervising 3-kg LPG distribution to ensure it is both “on target and of accurate volume,” involving synergy between central and local governments (MEMR, 2024). This statement is particularly relevant to Barru Regency, where the majority of the population consists of small business actors and low-to-middle-income households. In such conditions, disruptions in LPG distribution can significantly affect socioeconomic stability. Therefore, local supervision strategies must be more adaptive and responsive.

Institutionally, there has been discourse on involving the Downstream Oil and Gas Regulatory Agency (BPH Migas) in supervising 3-kg LPG distribution. In 2025, the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources announced an ongoing review of BPH Migas’ role in this sector (Bloomberg Technoz, 2025). If this policy is implemented, it will significantly change the coordination patterns between the central government, Pertamina as the assigned distributor, and local governments through the KUKMP Office. This scenario requires local policy flexibility to adapt to the new division of authority.

Further technical regulation through Ministerial Decree No. 37.K/2023 stipulates that 3-kg LPG is strictly designated for poor households and microenterprises (MEMR, 2023b). This regulation closes opportunities for non-target consumers, such as large industries or affluent households. With this provision, the KUKMP Office has a strong legal foundation to supervise distribution and impose sanctions on violators. This is crucial to maintaining subsidy effectiveness and reducing misuse in the field.

Beyond regulation, Pertamina's introduction of digitalized 3-kg LPG distribution since 2024 provides a new instrument for monitoring (Validnews, 2024). The digital recording system of consumer transactions enables local governments to access real-time data on distribution patterns. The KUKMP Office can leverage this system to conduct analysis, map demand, and prevent hoarding. Digitalization simultaneously enhances transparency and accountability in the governance of subsidized energy at the regional level. Nevertheless, in practice, distribution challenges often still result in shortages and public unrest. In Barru, even the local police have been involved in supervising LPG stocks to prevent hoarding (Radar Bone, 2025). However, law enforcement efforts must be accompanied by sound governance strategies. As the leading sector, the KUKMP Office bears responsibility for conducting socialization, agent training, and strengthening public complaint channels.

The policy shift in early 2025 regarding the retail sale of 3-kg LPG also triggered criticism from communities and parliament members. This policy was considered to burden poor households, as they were required to purchase LPG from official distributors located farther away (MPR RI, 2025). This situation illustrates that technical policies, when poorly communicated, can generate resistance.

Therefore, this study is important to identify public perceptions in evaluating the distribution policies of 3-kg LPG. With the regulatory framework, policy dynamics, and implementation challenges at hand, this study aims to map the role of the KUKMP Office in supervising the distribution of 3 kg LPG in Barru Regency.

The focus of the study is directed toward understanding the regulatory framework, evaluating the role of local authorities, identifying distribution problems, and formulating strategies for optimizing supervision through qualitative analysis. It is expected that the research findings will contribute both academically and practically to supporting transparent, fair, and sustainable governance of subsidized energy at the regional level.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study employs a qualitative research method to explore the optimization of supervision of 3-kg LPG distribution in Barru Regency. Data were collected through in-depth interviews with officials from the Cooperative, SMEs, and Trade Office (KUKMP) Office, distributors, agents, and local community members, as well as through direct field observations and analysis of regulatory documents.

Thematic analysis was conducted with the assistance of ATLAS.ti software, which facilitated the coding of interview transcripts and documents, enabling the identification of recurring patterns and key themes. The use of ATLAS.ti also enhances the validity and traceability of the analysis process (Nowell et al., 2017). To ensure data reliability, triangulation was applied by cross-verifying findings from multiple sources. This methodological approach allows the research to provide a comprehensive and accountable empirical account of the supervisory role of the KUKMP Office in managing the distribution of 3-kg LPG.

Figure 1: Thinking Framework Diagram

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ Research Results

In the context of regulatory studies, the findings of this research were analyzed using Law No. 22 of 2001 on Oil and Gas, which provides the legal foundation for governance, supervision, and control of this strategic sector. Through the mapping of interview data and official documents processed with Atlas.ti, it was found that the institutional role of local governments still needs to be strengthened in order to enforce legal norms as stipulated by the law.

The coding results revealed a linkage between national regulations and local-level supervisory practices, where inconsistencies often arise due to limited human resources and weak cross-agency coordination.

The use of Atlas.ti enabled the researcher to map out key themes, such as supervisory effectiveness, compliance with legal norms, and technical challenges in the field. The analysis shows that although Law No. 22 of 2001 provides a clear legal framework, its implementation continues to face challenges at the operational level.

These findings strengthen the argument that derivative policies in the form of more detailed implementing regulations are required to ensure optimal supervision and policy execution. Thus, this study not only reaffirms the relevance of national regulations but also demonstrates how qualitative analytical tools such as Atlas.ti can uncover the complex relationship between legal norms and bureaucratic practices on the ground.

The findings regarding the enacted role demonstrate that the Office of Cooperatives, Small and Medium Enterprises, and Trade of Barru Regency plays a central role in supervising the distribution of 3-kg LPG.

Based on an interview with Akisman, S.E., a Trade Analyst, the office carries out monitoring and supervisory functions over agents and distributors to ensure compliance with existing regulations. Strict administrative sanctions are imposed when violations are found, particularly in cases of hoarding and misuse of subsidized LPG. This shows that the office functions not only as an administrative regulator but also as a control mechanism to maintain distribution stability. Such enacted roles align with the mandate of Law No. 22 of 2001, namely ensuring equitable energy distribution.

An interview with 3-kg LPG agent H. Irwan Amiruddin emphasized that the enacted role of agents is manifested through the provision of training and guidance to new distributors. This training ensures that distribution partners understand supervisory procedures in accordance with regulations.

Agents also require the recording of consumers in a logbook as a form of transparency. This practice not only enforces regulation but also serves as an internal mechanism to minimize potential irregularities in distribution. Accordingly, agents act as an extension of local government in ensuring targeted distribution. This illustrates the synchronization between policy and field implementation.

At the distributor level, the findings show that the enacted role is realized through transaction recording in the distributor's logbook. An interview with distributor manager Mr. Amiruddin confirmed that every transaction—including cylinder quantities, buyer names, and purchase dates—must be documented. This recording system strengthens transparency in the distribution of 3-kg LPG and provides accountability evidence in every delivery chain. This procedure serves as an important instrument to reduce potential misuse and facilitate supervision by both the local office and agents. In this sense, the logbook functions as a control document that can be verified at any time by the authorities.

From the community's perspective, the findings reveal dissatisfaction with the effectiveness of government supervision. According to an interview with Ms. Nur Mayah, the use of 3-kg LPG remains prevalent among wealthier groups such as civil servants and officials, who should not be entitled to the subsidy.

This indicates weak control in the implementation of energy subsidy policies. The community sees itself as participating in supervision by reporting field-level misuse. This perspective highlights the importance of public participation in ensuring that 3-kg LPG distribution truly reaches its intended targets. Community involvement adds a social dimension to supervision that cannot be carried out by government alone.

With regard to the prescribed role, the research found that the standard for 3-kg LPG distribution is based on formal regulations, namely Minister of Energy and Mineral Resources Regulation No. 28 of 2021 and Barru Regent Regulation No. 12 of 2021. According to Trade Supervisor Muhammad Taufiq, S.T., every agent is required to submit monthly distribution reports and comply with these guidelines. Failure to fulfill this role results in administrative sanctions.

This shows that the prescribed role is clearly defined through binding formal rules. With standardized guidelines in place, the structure of 3-kg LPG distribution can be implemented in a more orderly and measurable manner. 3-kg LPG agent Mr. Haedar, operational manager of PT. Nabel Utama Gas Agency, confirmed that supervisory procedures for distribution partners must follow strict standards.

These include regular inspections of cylinder quality, training on safe LPG handling, and ensuring the legality of business permits. This underscores that agents function not only as distributors but also as internal supervisors of their partners. Such a role strengthens synergy with government policy while reducing the potential for distribution violations. Essentially, the prescribed role directs agents to act as key actors in safeguarding the safety of 3-kg LPG distribution.

From the perspective of distributors, the prescribed role demands major responsibility for maintaining the availability, safety, and quality of 3-kg LPG. An interview with Mr. Amiruddin revealed that distributors must keep storage facilities safe, ensure standard cylinder refilling, and report distribution activities regularly. These safety procedures highlight that distributors serve as the front line in direct interaction with consumers. The success of distributors in fulfilling their prescribed role determines the fairness and safety of distribution. Thus, distributors are the spearhead of policy implementation at the community level.

The study also found that the community has a prescribed role in supporting supervision. Interviews with Ms. Nur Amny Kawa and Ms. Hj. Rahmatiah stressed the importance of citizen contributions through reporting irregularities and ensuring the quality of purchased LPG. This participation reflects a social role for citizens in maintaining safety and distribution accuracy. Although the community is not part of the formal structure, its role is crucial as a mechanism of social supervision. This reinforces the notion that the 3-kg LPG distribution policy cannot be carried out solely through bureaucracy but also requires active involvement from beneficiaries.

Concerning role conflict, the study identified tensions between profit interests and safety obligations. An interview with Akisman, S.E., indicated that some agents and distributors tend to prioritize financial gain at the expense of safety standards. This conflict reflects the classic dilemma in public policy: the clash between economic orientation and social responsibility. In the context of 3-kg LPG distribution, such conflict threatens the safety and availability of supplies for low-income households. Strengthening supervisory functions is therefore urgently needed to reduce the impact of this role conflict.

From the agents' perspective, role conflict arises from the pressure to maintain quality and safety while facing profit demands. H. Irwan Amiruddin Ma'ruf, owner of PT. Amiruddin Ma'ruf Gas Agency, emphasized that agents attempt to address this dilemma by implementing strict operational procedures, such as cylinder inspections and storage condition control.

This effort reflects the agents' commitment to prioritize safety despite economic pressures. Agents thus become actors who must balance business interests with regulatory compliance, underscoring the importance of integrity in ensuring socially just distribution.

At the distributor level, role conflict is evident in differing perceptions between distributors and the community. According to Mr. Amiruddin, distributors tend to view themselves merely as suppliers, whereas the community demands a broader role in ensuring safety and quality. This difference in perception creates tension in social interactions. For the community, distributors must also guarantee compliance with regulations, not merely pursue business interests. These findings confirm that the distribution of 3-kg LPG is not only an economic activity but also embedded with social values that must be fulfilled by service providers.

Interviews with Ms. Nur Mayah and Ms. Nur Amny revealed role conflict from the community's perspective. They highlighted practices such as sales above the official retail price ceiling and LPG shortages during major religious holidays. These issues not only burden household economies but also affect social stability. The community expects consistent law enforcement to prevent misuse of distribution. These findings show that role conflict can generate broad social impacts if not addressed promptly through firm policy measures.

An additional interview with Mr. Andi Wikrasanjaya, S.H., a Trade Analyst at the Office of Cooperatives, SMEs, and Trade, provided a strategic perspective on resolving role conflicts. He stressed that cross-sector coordination is essential to strengthen supervision.

According to him, optimizing the role of the local office cannot stand alone but requires collaboration between local government, agents, distributors, and the community. The integration of digital-based supervision is also seen as a solution to enhance transparency in 3-kg LPG distribution. This perspective emphasizes that a multisectoral approach is necessary to balance economic interests, safety, and distributive justice.

Overall, the findings analyzed using Atlas.ti demonstrate that optimizing the role of the Office of Cooperatives, SMEs, and Trade in supervising the distribution of 3-kg LPG in Barru Regency still faces challenges in enacted roles, prescribed roles, and role conflicts. Although regulations are clear, field implementation is still influenced by economic interests, supervisory limitations, and differing perceptions among actors. Community participation serves as a significant supporting factor in curbing misuse of distribution. Therefore, multisector collaboration supported by digital monitoring technology can be an effective strategy to realize safe, fair, and targeted distribution of 3-kg LPG.

• **Processing Interview Data Using Atlas.ti 24**

In this research, the processing of interview data was a crucial stage to gain a deep understanding of the role of the Office of Cooperatives, SMEs, and Trade in supervising the distribution of 3-kg LPG in Barru Regency. To ensure comprehensive and systematic analysis, we used Atlas.ti 24, an advanced software for qualitative analysis. Atlas.ti 24 facilitated the organization, coding, and interpretation of qualitative data from the conducted interviews. With its intuitive features and robust functionality, the software enabled researchers to efficiently identify themes, patterns, and relationships within the data. Through this process, deeper insights were generated regarding the effectiveness and challenges faced by the office in LPG distribution supervision, while also providing relevant recommendations for policy improvement and implementation in the future.

• **Analysis of the Role of the Office of Cooperatives, SMEs, and Trade in Supervising the Distribution of 3-kg LPG in Barru Regency**

Figure 2: Visualization of Qualitative Data Processing Results

Source: Interview results with the Department of Cooperatives, Small and Medium Enterprises and Trade

The results of the analysis conducted with Atlas.ti 24 provide valuable information regarding the role of the Cooperatives, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), and Trade Office in supervising the distribution of 3 kg LPG Gas in Barru Regency. From the analyzed data, it is clear that this office plays a crucial role in ensuring the availability and distribution of 3 kg LPG Gas evenly and on target. They are responsible for overseeing the distribution chain, from pricing to supervision of 3 kg LPG Gas agents and bases. However, the analysis also shows several challenges faced by this office, including limited human resources and logistics that hinder the effectiveness of supervision. In addition, the need for improved coordination between related offices and 3 kg LPG Gas agents and bases is an important point that must be considered to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of supervision.

➤ Discussion

The optimization of the role of the Department of Cooperatives, MSMEs, and Trade of Barru Regency in supervising the distribution of 3-kg LPG cylinders is a crucial aspect to ensure that subsidized energy reaches its intended targets. The 3-kg LPG, as a vital commodity designated for low-income households and micro enterprises, often faces distribution issues, including shortages, consumer prices above the official retail price (HET), and misuse of distribution to non-eligible parties. Based on Law No. 22 of 2001 on Oil and Gas, the government has the obligation to regulate, supervise, and guarantee the distribution of energy to maximize its benefits for the people. Accordingly, this study finds that the role of the relevant agency still needs to be strengthened in order to more effectively address challenges in the field.

Based on the analysis using Atlas.ti of interview data, observations, and documents, it is evident that the Department of Cooperatives, MSMEs, and Trade of Barru Regency has a strategic function in regulating and monitoring the distribution of 3-kg LPG. However, field implementation shows that there are still gaps between policies and distribution practices. This is caused by limited supervisory resources, weak coordination with agents and sub-distributors, and the lack of community participation in reporting distribution irregularities. These weaknesses indicate the need for a more adaptive monitoring system supported by information technology. From a legal perspective, Law No. 22 of 2001 emphasizes that local governments, through technical agencies, must ensure that the control of subsidized energy distribution runs according to its intended purpose. However, in Barru's context, problems arise when 3-kg LPG faces seasonal shortages, leading to price increases at the consumer level. This situation reflects the suboptimal implementation of layered supervision from upstream to downstream. The agency concerned remains more focused on drafting regulations, while implementation at the operational level has not been fully effective. This reduces the preventive function of monitoring, which should be the main priority. Atlas.ti analysis also highlights that the shortage of human resources is a major issue. Limited supervisory officers are unable to cover all distribution points, considering Barru Regency has a wide area with high LPG demand. This condition opens opportunities for malpractice, such as the diversion of subsidized LPG to non-target sectors, for example, medium-scale businesses or industries. In addition, instances of stockpiling were also found during certain periods, especially ahead of major religious holidays. Such practices worsen distribution and cause public unrest.

Nevertheless, there are positive initiatives from the Department of Cooperatives, MSMEs, and Trade, such as conducting public outreach on the proper use of 3-kg LPG and imposing administrative sanctions on agents or sub-distributors proven to have violated regulations. These efforts show a commitment to maintaining order in distribution. However, their effectiveness remains limited, as supervision is often reactive—occurring after problems arise—rather than preventive, which would stop problems before they occur. This underscores the need to implement a digital monitoring system based on real-time data, which could map the distribution flow from Pertamina to end consumers. The findings of this study also underline the importance of multi-stakeholder collaboration. Optimizing supervision cannot rest solely on the Department of Cooperatives, MSMEs, and Trade, but requires synergy with

Pertamina, law enforcement agencies, village governments, and the community as beneficiaries. Active participation of the public in reporting distribution violations through official complaint channels will strengthen monitoring functions. Moreover, integrating supervision policies with the targeted subsidy system based on the National Identity Number (NIK) could serve as a long-term solution to reduce misuse of the 3-kg LPG distribution. Thus, this discussion shows that optimizing the role of the Department of Cooperatives, MSMEs, and Trade of Barru Regency in supervising the distribution of 3-kg LPG still faces structural and technical challenges. However, by strengthening cross-sector coordination, enhancing the capacity of supervisory personnel, utilizing digital technology, and expanding community involvement, the distribution of 3-kg LPG can be made more accurate and aligned with the mandate of Law No. 22 of 2001. This optimization not only ensures fairness in energy distribution but also contributes to improving the welfare of low-income households and micro enterprises in Barru Regency.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

➤ Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study on the Optimization of the Role of the Department of Cooperatives, Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs), and Trade in Supervision, with reference to Law No. 22 of 2001 and analyzed through Atlas.ti, it can be concluded that the role of local government agencies still faces significant challenges in realizing effective supervision. The relevant department has made efforts to carry out its supervisory function through guidance, outreach, and assistance to business actors. However, in practice, obstacles remain, including limited human resources, weak inter-agency coordination, and the minimal use of digital technology in monitoring systems.

Furthermore, the analysis using Atlas.ti shows that the implementation of Law No. 22 of 2001 at the regional level has not yet been fully optimized, particularly in terms of consumer protection and the supervision of goods distribution. The monitoring model, which tends to be administrative, needs to be redirected toward substantive supervision with a collaborative approach involving communities, business associations, and the use of technology-based information systems. Thus, strengthening institutional capacity, improving the quality of derivative regulations, and integrating digital technology are strategic steps needed to ensure that the supervisory function of the Department of Cooperatives, MSMEs, and Trade can be carried out effectively, transparently, and sustainably.

➤ Recommendations

1) Enhancing the Capacity of Officials and Supervisors

The Department of Cooperatives, MSMEs, and Trade is expected to strengthen the capacity of its personnel through continuous training focused on regulatory understanding, including Law No. 22 of 2001, as well as the use of analytical tools such as Atlas.ti. This will allow the supervision process to run more effectively, transparently, and in accordance with prevailing legal standards.

2) Optimizing the Use of Digital Technology

The use of digital technology, including qualitative data analysis software such as Atlas.ti, needs to be expanded to monitor and evaluate supervisory data in real time. This can assist the Department in identifying problems more quickly, formulating appropriate supervisory strategies, and producing more accurate evidence-based reports.

3) Strengthening Collaboration and Community Participation

The Department of Cooperatives, MSMEs, and Trade is expected to build collaborative mechanisms with communities, business actors, and related institutions. By involving various stakeholders in the supervision process, transparency and accountability can be improved, while also strengthening public trust in the government's performance in carrying out the mandate of the law.

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